

URGANCH DAVLAT TIBBIYOT INSTITUTI JANUBIY OROLBO‘YI TIBBIYOT JURNALI 2 - TOM, 3 - SON. 2026

14.00.00 - TIBBIYOT FANLARI ISSN: 3093-8740

SURUNKALI ATROFIK GASTRIT BILAN KASALLANGAN BEMORLARDA PSIXOEMOTSIONAL BUZILISHLAR KLINIK STRUKTURASI VA PSIXOKORREKSIYASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada rivojlangan surunkali gastrit bo‘lgan bemorlarda psixoemotsional buzilishlarning klinik strukturasi psixodiagnostik so‘rovnomalar yordamida baholandi. Takomillashtirilgan psixokorreksion metodlar yordamida korreksiya o‘tkazilgan holda davolashdan oldingi va keyingi natijalar statistik tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so‘zlar: surunkali gastrit, xavotir, rigidlik, frusturatsiya, agressivlik

КЛИНИЧЕСКАЯ СТРУКТУРА ПСИХОЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ НАРУШЕНИЙ И ПСИХОКОРРЕКЦИЯ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ХРОНИЧЕСКИМ АТРОФИЧЕСКИМ ГАСТРИТОМ

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Аннотация: В данной статье клиническая структура психоэмоциональных нарушений у пациентов с развившимся хроническим гастритом оценивалась с помощью психодиагностических опросников. Проведена коррекция с использованием усовершенствованных психокоррекционных методов, а результаты до и после лечения подверглись статистическому анализу.

Ключевые слова: хронический гастрит, тревожность, ригидность, фрустрация, агрессивность

CLINICAL STRUCTURE OF PSYCHO-EMOTIONAL DISORDERS AND PSYCHOCORRECTION IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC ATROPHIC GASTRITIS

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Annotation: In this article, the clinical structure of psycho-emotional disorders in patients with advanced chronic gastritis was assessed using psychodiagnostic questionnaires. Correction was carried out with improved psychocorrectional methods, and the results before and after treatment were statistically analyzed.

Keywords: chronic gastritis, anxiety, rigidity, frustration, aggressiveness

Surunkali atrofik gastrit (SAG) dunyo bo'yicha eng keng tarqalgan ovqat hazm qilish kasalliklaridan biridir va u oshqozon saratonining eng ko'p uchraydigan oldindan belgilovchi holatidir [1–3]. Dunyo bo'yicha taxminan 25 % tarqalishga ega bo'lib, global sog'liqni saqlash tizimiga katta yuk bo'lib qolmoqda. SAG bilan og'rikan bemorlarda oshqozon saratoni rivojlanish xavfi yil sayin ortib bormoqda, yillik o'sish taxminan 0,1 % ni tashkil etadi. 2020 yilga nisbatan 2040 yilga kelib oshqozon saratoni uchrash chastotasi 47 % ga oshishi kutilmoqda [1,28,29,36]. Bundan tashqari surunkali atrofik gastrit (SAG) so'nggi yillarda bemorlarning o'rtacha yoshi pasayishi bilan SAGning uchrash chastotasi ortdi [4]. SAG surunkali gastritdan rivojlanadi va ko'pincha bir necha yil davomida infeksiya va oshqozon shilliq qavatining yallig'lanishidan kelib chiqadi. Yallig'lanish natijasida oshqozon hujayralarining normal tuzilishi uzoq muddatda buzilishi, bezlarning kamayishi va hujayralarning funksional yetishmovchiligi oxir-oqibat shilliq qavatning qisqarishiga olib keladi [5–7]. SAGning dastlabki bosqichida bemorlarda odatda aniq simptomlar bo'lmaydi, biroq ba'zida yuqori qorin bo'shlig'ida dam bo'lish, og'riq, ishtahaning yo'qolishi va ko'ngil aynishi kuzatiladi [8,9]. H. pylori infeksiyasi sababli SAG rivojlangan bemorlarda gastroezofageal reflyuks [10], gemolitik anemiya [11] va suyak metabolizmi buzilishlari [12,13] kabi boshqa asoratlar ham uchrashi mumkin. Uzoq muddatli SAG bilan og'rikan bemorlarda depressiya uchrash chastotasi ≈ 50 % deb qayd etilgan va depressiya kasallik davomiyligi bilan ijobiy bog'liq bo'lgan [14], hatto tezlashtirilgan qarish bilan izohlangan [15]. Eng muhim jihati shundaki, SAG bilan og'rikan bemorlarda oshqozon saratonining yillik uchrash chastotasi 0,004–0,3 % ni tashkil etadi, bu SAGni ushbu xavfli kasallik uchun muhim xavf omili sifatida ko'rsatadi [15–18]. SAGning sabablari orasida H. pylori infeksiyasi, ovqatlanish, genetika, immunologik va boshqa omillar mavjud [17]. Uzoq muddatli xavotir va depressiya ham SAG uchun xavf omillari sifatida qayd etilgan [18]. Patogenezdagi farqlarga ko'ra, atrofik gastrit SAG va autoimmun atrofik gastritga bo'linadi [19,21]. SAGning asosiy sababi H. pylori infeksiyasidir. Infeksiya oshqozon bo'ylab parietal hujayralarning parchalanishiga olib keladi va oxir-oqibat shilliq qavatning qisqarishiga sabab bo'ladi [22–24]. H. pylori bilan zararlangan bemorlarda saraton rivojlanish xavfi infeksiyasizlarga qaraganda yuqoriroq [25]. Autoimmun atrofik gastrit, shuningdek, A-tur gastrit deb ham ataladi, bu organ-spesifik immun vositachiligidagi kasallik bo'lib, oshqozon fundusi va tanasidagi devor hujayralarining immun yo'li bilan buzilishi natijasida shilliq qavatning atrofiyasiga olib keladi [26–29]. Shu bilan birga ovqat hazm qilish tizimi kasalliklari va kayfiyat hamda xavotir buzilishlari o'rtasidagi munosabatga qiziqish doimiy bo'lib kelmoqda. Bir qator klinik va epidemiologik tadqiqotlar kayfiyat va xavotir buzilishlari bilan keng tarqalgan ovqat hazm qilish kasalliklari, jumladan, oshqozon yarasi, irritabiy ichak sindromi va Kron kasalligi o'rtasida sezilarli bog'liqlikni aniqlagan (Dunlop va boshq., 2003; Goodwin va boshq., 2006; Mawdsley va Rampton, 2005; Mayer, 2000; Mayer va boshq., 2001; Schwarz va boshq., 1993; Walker va boshq., 2008; Whitehead va boshq., 2002). Bir nechta klinik tadqiqotlar gastrit bilan og'rikan bemorlarning ayrim guruhlarida depressiv simptomlarning yuqori darajada ekanligini (Magni va boshq., 1982; Solov'eva va boshq., 1997) hamda umumiy gastroenterologik ambulator bemorlar orasida kayfiyat va xavotir buzilishlari tashxislarining yuqori

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darajada uchrashini hujjatlashtirgan (Jiang va boshq., 2009). [26–29]. Shunga qaramay, gastrit va ruhiy buzilishlar o‘rtasidagi munosabatga oid ba’zi muhim savollar hali ham javobsiz qolmoqda. Shu maqsadda mazkur tadqiqot ishida surunkali gastrit rivojlangan bemorlarda psixoemotsional buzilishlar klinik strukturasi aniqlash va korreksiya qilishga e’tibor qaratiladi. [32–35]

Maqsad: Surunkali atrofik gastrit rivojlangan bemorlarda psixoemotsional buzilishlar strukturasi aniqlash va unda psixokorreksiya o‘tkazish

Material va metodlar: Urganch davlat tibbiyot institute klinikasida psixoemotsional buzilishlar rivojlangan surunkali atrofik gastrit tashxisi bilan davolanib yurgan 46 ta bemor kuzatuvga olindi va ikki guruhga ajratildi. Shundan 23 bemor birinchi guruhga, 23 ta bemor ikkinchi guruhga birlashtirildi Bemorlarimiz psixoemotsional buzilishlar darajasini aniqlashda Ayzenk (bemorlarning o‘z ruhiy holatini baholash) so‘rovnomasidan foydalanildi.

Bemorlarda o‘tkazilgan psixoterapevtik usullardan ratsional psixoterapiya va kognitiv-bixeviorial psixoterapiya tanlab olindi, bemorlarimizning taqsimlanishi quyidagicha ko‘rinishda bo‘ldi

Tadqiqotimizda psixoemotsional buzilishlar psixokorreksiyasi bemorlarni ikkita guruhga ajratilgan holda olib borildi:

1 chi asosiy (n=23) guruhdagi bemorlarimizda bazis davoga+kognitiv-bixeviorial psixoterapiya, 2 chi taqqoslash (n=23) guruhida bazis davoga+psixoeukativ terapiya bilan birgalikda 2 oy davomida ambulator sharoitda olib borildi. Olingan ko‘rsatkichlar statistik tahlil qilingan holda, quyidagi natijalar olindi.

Bemorlarda o‘tkazilgan psixoterapevtik usullardan ratsional psixoterapiya va kognitiv-bixeviorial psixoterapiya tanlab olindi, bemorlarimizning taqsimlanishi quyidagicha ko‘rinishda bo‘ldi: (1-jadval)

	1-guruh		2-guruh		Jami	
	abs.	%	abs.	%	abs.	%
A	11	47,8	11	47,8	22	47,8
E	12	52,2	12	52,2	24	52,2
Yoshi	35,0±0,9		36,1±1,0		35,2±1,1	

Unga ko‘ra 1-guruhdagi bemorlarimizning 12 (52,2%) i erkaklar, 11 (47,8%) i ayollar bo‘lib, ularning o‘rtacha yosh ko‘rsatkichi 35,0±0,9 tashkil qildi, 2-guruhdagi bemorlarning 12 (52,2%) i erkaklar, 11 (47,8%) i ayollar bo‘lib, ularning o‘rtacha yoshi 36,1±1,0 ni tashkil qildi. Olingan ko‘rsatkichlarni tahlil qilishda statistika usularidan (foizli tahlil, Studentning t-mezoni, r-qiyamtni hisoblash orqali natijalarining ishoniligi baholangan, olingan natijalar p<0.05 asosida ishonchli deb topilgan.

Natijalar: Bemorlarimizda olib borilgan psixometrik tekshiruvlar ko‘rsatkichlari davodan oldingi va davodan keyingi statistik taxlil qilinganda quyidagi natijalar shakllandi (1-rasm).

Ayzenk so'rovnomalari ko'rsatkichlari, % (davodan oldin 1-guruh)

Unga ko'ra 1-guruhdagi (n=23) bemorlarimizda Ayzenk so'rovnomasi bo'yicha, havotir 13% (n=3) ida aniqlanmadi $7,0 \pm 0,0$, 65,2% (n=15) ida o'rta $12,8 \pm 0,21$, 22% (n=5) ida yuqori darajada $17,8 \pm 0,25$, agressivlik 17,4% (n=4) ida aniqlanmadi $7,0 \pm 0,0$, 61% (n=14) ida o'rta $12,0 \pm 0,18$, 22% (n=5) ida yuqori darajada $18,0 \pm 0,0$, frusturatsiya 26% (n=6) ida aniqlanmadi $7,0 \pm 0,0$, 65% (n=15) ida o'rta $12,6 \pm 0,16$, 9% (n=2) ida yuqori darajada $18,3 \pm 0,21$, rigidlik 22% (n=5) ida aniqlanmadi $7,0 \pm 0,0$, 65% (n=15) ida o'rta $12,7 \pm 0,21$, 13% (n=3) ida yuqori darajada $18,0 \pm 1,5$ ekanligi aniqlandi, 2 guruhda bemorlarimizda olinga Ayzenk so'rovnomasi ko'rsatkichlar quyidagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ldi (2-rasm).

Ayzenk so'rovnomalari ko'rsatkichlari, % (davodan oldin 2-guruh)

Taqqoslash guruhidagi bemorlarda esa havotir darajasi 13% (n=3) ida aniqlanmadi $6,4 \pm 0,1$, 74% (n=17) ida o'rta $12,6 \pm 0,21$, 13% (n=3) ida yuqori darajada $17,6 \pm 0,18$, agressivlik 17,4% (n=4) ida

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aniqlanmadi $7,0 \pm 0,0$, 69,5% (n=16) ida o‘rta $11,7 \pm 0,23$, 13% (n=3) ida yuqori darajada $17,0 \pm 0,58$, frusturatsiya 17% (n=4) ida aniqlanmadi $7,0 \pm 0,0$, 78,3% (n=18) ida o‘rta $12,4 \pm 0,22$, 4.3% (n=1) ida yuqori darajada $18,6 \pm 0,24$, rigidlik 22% (n=5) ida aniqlanmadi $7,0 \pm 0,0$, 70% (n=16) ida o‘rta $12,3 \pm 0,24$, 8% (n=2) ida yuqori darajada $19,3 \pm 0,48$ ekanligi aniqlandi.

Bemorlarda olib borilgan ko‘rsatkichlar korreksiyadan oldingi psixometrik ko‘rsatkichlar statistik jihatdan sezilarli darajada farq qilmaganligi aniqlandi ($p > 0,05$). Bemorlarimizda olib borilgan psixokorreksiya natijasida quyidagi ko‘rsatkichlar shakllandi va statistik tahlil qilindi (3-4 rasmlar).

Davodan keyin 1-guruhdagi (n=23) bemorlarimizda Ayzenk so‘rovnomasi bo‘yicha, havotir 65,2% (n=15) ida aniqlanmadi $6,4 \pm 0,12$, 34,8% (n=8) ida o‘rta $9,1 \pm 0,26$, agressivlik 69,6% (n=16) ida aniqlanmadi $6,3 \pm 0,09$, 30,4% (n=7) ida o‘rta $8,7 \pm 0,16$, frusturatsiya 65,2% (n=15) ida aniqlanmadi $6,4 \pm 0,10$, 34,8% (n=8) ida o‘rta $8,4 \pm 1,0$, rigidlik 73,9% (n=17) ida aniqlanmadi $6,4 \pm 0,11$, 26,1% (n=6) ida o‘rta $8,7 \pm 0,13$ pasayganligi aniqlandi ($p < 0,001$). Taqqoslash guruhida esa bu ko‘rsatkichlarda nisbatan statistik farqlanish borligi aniqlandi, unga ko‘ra 2-chi guruhda

Davodan keyin 2-guruhdagi ($n=23$) bemorlarimizda Ayzenk so'rovnomasi bo'yicha, havotir 34,7% ($n=8$) da aniqlanmadi $6,2 \pm 0,11$, 65,2% ($n=15$) da o'rta $9,1 \pm 0,26$, agressivlik 39,1% ($n=9$) da aniqlanmadi $6,4 \pm 0,1$, 61% ($n=14$) da o'rta $8,8 \pm 0,2$, frusturatsiya 43,5% ($n=9$) da aniqlanmadi $6,3 \pm 0,1$, 56,5% ($n=14$) da o'rta $8,2 \pm 1,0$, rigidlik 43,5% ($n=9$) da aniqlanmadi $6,4 \pm 0,12$, 56,5% ($n=14$) da o'rta $8,4 \pm 0,3$ pasayganligi aniqlandi ($p < 0,001$). Asosiy guruh va taqqoslash guruhida ko'rsatkichlar o'zaro solishtirilganda 1 chi guruh bemorlarida 2 chi guruhga nisbatan statistik farqlanish bilan o'zgarish kuzatilganligi aniqlandi.

Xulosa: Olingan natijalardan shuni xulosa qilish mumkinki, surunkali atrofik gastrit bilan kuzatuvga olingan bemorlarimizda psixoadaptatsion buzilishlar yuqori ekanligi aniqlandi, o'tkazilgan psixoterapevtik davo muolajalaridan so'ng asosiy guruhdagi bemorlarimizda havotir, frusturatsiya, agressivlik va rigidlik darajalarining, 2 chi guruhdagi bemorlarimizga nisbatan sezilarli darajada pasayganligi, bu esa o'z navbatida bu bemorlarda orol bo'yi muxitida va shunga o'xshash noqulay klimatga ega bo'lgan sharoitda yashovchi axolida somatik kasalliklar natijasida rivojlanuvchi psixoadaptatsion va psixoemotsional buzilishlarni korreksiya qilishda kognitiv-bixeviorial terapiyani standart davolash jarayonlariga tadbiiq qilish samarali natijalarga erishishiga turtki bo'lishi kuzatuvlarimizda o'z isbotini topdi.

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